

Mono-substituted Carbohydrazides, their Typical Derivatives and Formation of Heterocyclic Compounds from them.

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Although carbohydrazide and its *sym.*-diphenyl-derivative have been prepared by Curtius and Reich (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1895, ii, 52, 469), Skinner and Ruheman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 53, 550). Cazeneuve and Moreau (*Compt. rend.*, 1899, 129, 1256), Fischer and Heller, (*Annalen*, 1891, 263, 277, 269), Fischer (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1935) and Pellizary (*Gazzetta*, 1886, 16, 200), monosubstituted carbohydrazides are not known. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to make a comparative study of mono-substituted carbohydrazides and their derivatives with those of monosubstituted thiocarbohydrazides (Guha and Roy-Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 149, 163).

Phenyl-, *o*-tolyl- and *p*-tolyl-carbohydrazides have now been prepared by the action of hydrazine hydrate upon the corresponding ethyl carbazates, thus :

(R = Ph, *o*-tolyl, and *p*-tolyl)

But the reaction between phenylhydrazine and ethyl phenyl-carbazate did not take place.

Phenyl-, *o*- and *p*-tolyl-carbohydrazides react with aldehydes to give carbohydrazones of the type, $\text{RNH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{N}:\text{CHR}'$ (R = Ph, R' = Ph, cinnamyl, *o*-chlorophenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, *m*-bromophenyl, *o*-nitrophenyl, *m*-nitrophenyl, *o*-hydroxyphenyl; R = *o*-tolyl, R' = Ph, *o*- and *p*-chlorophenyl, *o*- and *p*-nitrophenyl, *m*-bromophenyl, *o*-hydroxyphenyl; R = *p*-tolyl, R' = Ph). *m*-Phthalaldehyde and 1-phenyl- and 1-*p*-tolyl-carbohydrazide gave respectively $m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}:\text{N}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{N}\cdot\text{H}\cdot\text{NHPh})_2$ and $m\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}=\text{N}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}_3)_2$ while acetone yielded the expected compounds, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{N}:\text{CMe}_2$ and $\text{Me}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{N}:\text{CMe}_2$.

The oxidising and ring-closing action of ferric chloride upon 1-phenylcarbohydrazide was tried by analogy with a similar reaction of Guha and Roy-Chaudhury with the corresponding thio-compound where they obtained a thiodiazol (*loc. cit.*, p. 157). But, in the present instance, the reaction could not be made to take place even when the reactants were heated in a sealed tube.

Phenanthraquinone and phenylcarbohydrazide yield first of all the monophenylcarbohydrazone, which then assumes the azo-structure (I) by the migration of one hydrogen atom.

This loses a molecule of water forming a closed-ring compound (possibly II or III) which, being unstable, is converted into the compound (IV or V) by loss of nitrogen. The former structure is preferred as the compound is insoluble in alkali.

Similar reactions involving the elimination of nitrogen from heterocyclic compounds have recently been observed by De and Dutt (*private communication*) with compounds obtained from phenanthraquinone on the one hand and 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides, diarylaminoguanidines, etc., on the other.

Isatin yields the corresponding phenyl- or *o*-tolylcarbohydrazone. From isatin and phenylthiocarbohydrazide Guha and Roy-Choudhury (*loc. cit.*, p. 152) obtained a thiodiazine compound. Evidently, the sulphur atom of the thiocarbohydrazones can assume the thiol form readily, but the oxygen atom of the carbohydrazones cannot assume the hydroxylic form so easily.

Carbon bisulphide in presence of alcoholic potash reacts with the hydrazide at the ordinary temperature to yield the expected potassium dithiocarboxylate (VI). If, however, the reaction mixture

is boiled under reflux for several hours, the potassium salt yields 1-*N*-phenylmonothiourazine (VII), thus:

It will be seen that this reaction is quite similar to that observed by Guha and De (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1216) between carbon bisulphide and thiocarbohydrazide.

Chlorocarbonic ester reacts very readily to form carbethoxyphenylcarbohydrazide (VIII) which, on being treated with strong hydrochloric acid, is decomposed, thus:

The influence of the phenyl group of phenylcarbohydrazide in not allowing the reactions to proceed in the normal way (as in the case of the unsubstituted carbohydrazide) is well marked also in its behaviour towards carbamide. Instead of forming a *p*-urazine derivative (*vide* Guha and De, *loc. cit.*) it forms phenylcarbohydrazidecarbonamide (IX), thus:

Nitrous acid reacts with the hydrazide in a peculiar fashion yielding not the expected azoimide ($\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{N}_2$) but 1-phenyl-4-hydroxysemicarbazide (X) by the elimination of a molecule of nitrogen from the intermediate azo-compound, thus:

It might be mentioned in this connection that this is the first time that a 4-hydroxysemicarbazide has been prepared.

Phenylisocyanate and potassium cyanate react with phenylcarbohydrazide in the normal fashion to yield phenylcarbohydrazide-carbophenylamide, $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHPh}$ and phenylcarbohydrazidecarbonamide $\text{PhNH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}_2$, the latter

loc. cit.) does not very much resemble that of phenylcarbohydrazidecarbothiophenylamide in so far as the latter gives, on alkali treatment, two thiodiazole compounds (XIII and XIV),

and with hydrochloric acid, 2:5-diketotetrahydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole. Thiodiazoles of the type of (XI) have been prepared by Busch (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 320, 2328 ; 1902, **35**, 973 ; 1904, **37**, 2333 ; 1909, **42**, 4763 ; 1911, **44**, 561, 1580) and by Freund (*Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 4178) by the action of carbonyl chloride upon 1:4-diarylthiosemicarbazides, and by Guha and Sen (*loc. cit.*) by the action of urea upon 4-arylthiosemicarbazides.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1-Phenylcarbohydrazide.—About 30 experiments were performed to find out the best method of preparation of 1-phenylcarbohydrazide from phenylcarbazine ester and hydrazine hydrate in alcoholic solution under varying conditions of temperature (*viz.*, from 100° to 150° under reflux and in a sealed tube) and duration of heating (*viz.*, from 5 to 15 hours) as the result of which the method given below has been found to be the best.

A mixture of ethyl phenylcarbazine (10 g.) and hydrazine hydrate (8.5 g.) with 4 c.c. of absolute alcohol was heated in a sealed tube at 120-125° for 12 hours. A slight pressure was noticed inside the tube after the reaction. The solution was poured into water and the unaltered ester (4 g.) was filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated on a water-bath to a syrup which on being kept in a vacuum desiccator for 2 days formed a white crystalline mass. This was washed with ether to remove some tarry matters and was finally crystallised from alcohol (yield, 5.5 g.). It is readily soluble in water, alcohol and acetic acid and sparingly so in benzene, toluene and ether. (Found: N, 33.78. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{ON}_4$ requires N, 33.98 per cent.). When the temperature was kept low (say between 100° and 120°) most of the carbazine ester was recovered unchanged—whilst on the application of higher temperature (130°-150°) a brownish-yellow tarry product was obtained from which a small quantity of carbohydrazide

melting at 154° was isolated. (Found: N, 62·15. Calc., N, 62·22 per cent.).

Attempt to prepare sym-Diphenylcarbohydrazide.—A mixture of equivalent quantities of ethyl phenylcarbazinate and phenylhydrazine was heated in a sealed tube at 120°—125° and again at 140-150° when no reaction was found to have taken place.

Reaction with o-Phenylenediamine.—Ethyl phenylcarbazinate (10 g.) was thoroughly mixed with an equivalent quantity of *o*-phenylenediamine and heated on an oil-bath at 200-210° for several hours but no reaction was found to have taken place. Guha and Roy-Choudhury (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 168) prepared a benzothioltriazine by the action of *o*-phenylenediamine upon ethyl phenyldithiocarbazinate.

Ethyl o-Tolylcarbasinate.—To a mixture of *o*-tolylhydrazine and pyridine, 4 to 5 times the quantity of water was added and the solution cooled to 0°. To this solution one molecular proportion of ethyl chlorocarbonate was added drop by drop under brisk shaking when an oil separated which soon solidified. The crude product was washed with dilute acetic acid and was further purified by crystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 74—75° (yield quantitative).

1-o-Tolylcarbohydrazide.—A mixture of equivalent quantities of ethyl *o*-tolylcarbazinate (10 g.), hydrazine hydrate (4 g.) and absolute alcohol (4 c.c.) was heated in a sealed tube at 115-120° for 12 hours. The solution was then poured into water, when the unreacted ester (about 3 g.) precipitated out and the whole mass was thoroughly triturated in a mortar and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and the solid thus obtained crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 153° (yield, 4 g.). It is readily soluble in water, alcohol and acetic acid. (Found: N, 30·89. $C_8H_{13}ON_4$ requires N, 31·11 per cent.).

Ethyl p-Tolylcarbasinate.—It was prepared similarly as the phenyl derivative and crystallised from a large quantity of water; m.p. 89-90° (yield quantitative).

1-p-Tolylcarbohydrazide.—The method of preparation was the same as that of 1-*o*-tolylcarbohydrazide. It was crystallised from water; m.p. 148-149° (yield almost quantitative). It is readily soluble in water, alcohol and acetic acid. (Found: N, 31·56. $C_8H_{12}ON_4$ requires N, 31·11 per cent.)

Benzaldehyde-1-phenylcarbohydrazone.—Benzaldehyde (1 g.) and 1-phenylcarbohydrazide (1·6 g.) in alcoholic solution were heated

under reflux for a few minutes, when a white crystalline product separated out.

It was filtered, washed with alcohol and then crystallised from the same solvent, m. p. 210-211° (yield quantitative). (Found: N, 22.52. $C_{14}H_{14}ON_4$ requires N, 22.04 per cent.).

o-Chlorobenzaldehyde-1-*o*-tolylcarbohydrazone was similarly prepared and crystallised from acetic acid; m.p. 212-213°. (Found: N, 18.74. $C_{15}H_{15}OCIN_4$ requires N, 18.51 per cent.).

o-Chlorobenzaldehyde-1-phenylcarbohydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 212-213°.

p-Chlorobenzaldehyde-1-phenylcarbohydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 197-198°.

m-Bromobenzaldehyde-1-phenylcarbohydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 196-197°.

o-Nitrobenzaldehyde-1-phenylcarbohydrazone was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 208-209°.

m-Nitrobenzaldehyde-1-phenylcarbohydrazone, m.p. 243-244°.

Salicylaldehyde-1-phenylcarbohydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 222-223°. It is soluble in alkali and can be precipitated by acids.

Benzaldehyde-1-*o*-tolylcarbohydrazone, m.p. 201-202°, was crystallised from alcohol.

o-Chlorobenzaldehyde-1-*o*-tolylcarbohydrazone, m.p. 212-213°, was crystallised from acetic acid.

p-Chlorobenzaldehyde-1-*o*-tolylcarbohydrazone, m.p. 198°, was crystallised from acetic acid.

o-Nitrobenzaldehyde-1-*o*-tolylcarbohydrazone, m. p. 219°, was crystallised from acetic acid.

m-Nitrobenzaldehyde-1-*o*-tolylcarbohydrazone, m.p. 211-212°, was crystallised from acetic acid.

m-Bromobenzaldehyde-1-*o*-tolylcarbohydrazone, m.p. 216°, was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 216°. (Found: N, 16.27. $C_{15}H_{15}OBrN_4$ requires N, 16.13 per cent.).

Salicylaldehyde-1-*o*-tolylcarbohydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 218-219°. It is soluble in alkali and can be precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 19.68. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2N_4$ requires N, 19.71 per cent.).

Benzaldehyde-1-p-tolylcarbohydrazone was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 193-194°. (Found: N, 21.20. $C_{15}H_{16}ON_4$ requires N, 20.89 per cent.).

m-Phthalaldehyde-1-phenylcarbohydrazone, m.p. 266-267°. It is insoluble in almost all organic solvents and was purified by washing with boiling alcohol repeatedly.

m-Phthalaldehyde-1-o-tolylcarbohydrazone was prepared similarly. It was insoluble in almost all the organic solvents but slightly soluble in alcohol from which it was precipitated in an amorphous state, m.p. 236-237° (decomp.). (Found: N, 24.49. $C_{24}H_{26}O_2N_8$ requires N, 24.46 per cent.).

Acetone-1-phenylcarbohydrazone, m.p. 63°. (Found: N, 27.04. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_4$ requires N, 27.18 per cent.).

Acetone-1-o-tolylcarbohydrazone, m.p. 177°, was crystallised from acetone.

Action of Phenanthraquinone on 1-Phenylcarbohydrazide (IV).—Phenanthraquinone and 1-phenylcarbohydrazide (in equivalent quantities) were heated under reflux for 5-6 hours in acetic acid solution when nitrogen was found to evolve. The separated solid crystallised from nitrobenzene; m.p. 285° (decomp.). It is insoluble in acids and alkalis and is charred by concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 9.52. $C_{21}H_{14}ON_9$ requires N, 9.03 per cent.).

Isatin-1-phenylcarbohydrazone.—A mixture of 1-phenylcarbohydrazide and isatin in acetic acid was heated under reflux for about 4 hours. Within an hour the colour of the solution changed from red to yellow and a yellow precipitate came out of the solution. It was filtered, washed with acetic acid and crystallised from pyridine; m.p. 281° (decomp.). It is soluble in alkali and can be precipitated back by acids. (Found: N, 23.62. $C_{15}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 23.73 per cent.).

Isatin-o-tolylcarbohydrazone.—Molecular proportions of 1-o-tolylcarbohydrazide (1 g.) and isatin (0.81 g.) were heated in acetic acid solution for 2 hours. The separated yellow product crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 251—252° (decomp.). It is readily soluble in alkali from which solution it can be precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 23.98. $C_{16}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 22.65 per cent.).

Potassium 1-Phenylcarbohydrazide-dithiocarbonylate, PhNH·NH·CO·NH·NH·CS₂K (VI).—A molecular quantities of 1-phenylcarbohydrazide, carbon bisulphide and caustic potash in absolute alcohol on being allowed to stand for some time gave a white crystalline

substance which was further purified by crystallising from the same solvent. (Found : N, 20.02. $C_8H_9ON_4S_2K$ requires N, 19.93 per cent.).

1-Phenyl-6-thiol-8-keto-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydro-1:2:4:5-tetrazine (VII).—A mixture of equivalent quantities of 1-phenylcarbohydrazide, carbon bisulphide and caustic potash in absolute alcohol was heated under reflux at 60-70° for about 2 hours and subsequently on a water-bath for 4 hours. The pasty mass obtained after the removal of alcohol was dissolved in water, filtered and cautiously acidified with hydrochloric acid. On cooling, a white crystalline precipitate came out of the solution slowly and was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 206°. (Found : C, 46.51; H, 4.42; N, 27.06, 26.86. $C_8H_8ON_4S$ requires C, 46.15; H, 3.85; N, 27.32 per cent.).

5-Carboxy-1-phenylcarbohydrazide (VIII).—To a well cooled aqueous solution of 1-phenylcarbohydrazide an equivalent quantity of ethyl chlorocarbonate was added drop by drop. The white crystalline substance thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 202-203°. (Found : N, 23.94. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3N_4$ requires N, 23.52 per cent.).

Urea and 1-Phenylcarbohydrazide: Formation of 1-Phenylcarbohydrazide-5-carbonamide (IX).—An intimate mixture of molecular proportions of freshly dried urea and 1-phenylcarbohydrazide was heated on an oil-bath at 130-135° for 6-7 hours. First of all the mixture melted and the reaction proceeded with the evolution of ammonia. After about two hours the molten mass solidified, but as the evolution of ammonia still continued it was heated for 5 hours more. The solid was then crystallised thrice from water; m.p. 223° (decomp.). (Found : N, 33.56. $C_8H_{11}O_2N_5$ requires N, 33.49 per cent.)

Action of Nitrous Acid upon 1-Phenylcarbohydrazide: Formation of PhNH·NH·CO·NHOH (X).—To a mixture of ice-cold aqueous solution of 1-phenylcarbohydrazide (1 mol.), and sodium nitrite (1 mol.), ice-cold hydrochloric acid (2 mols.) was added drop by drop when nitrogen was found to evolve profusely. The separated yellow pasty mass which solidified on standing, was freed from the adhering oily impurity by pressing on a porous plate and was finally crystallised from 88 per cent. alcohol; m.p. 86°. It is insoluble in cold acid but dissolves in alkali on being gently warmed with a dull yellow coloration. (Found : C, 50.25; H, 5.58; N, 27.00, 26.81, 26.54. $C_7H_9O_2N_3$ requires C, 50.86; H, 5.40; N, 27.00 per cent.).

Action of Potassium Cyanate: Formation of (IX).—To an aqueous solution of the carbonylhydrazide an equivalent quantity of hydrochloric acid was added. The solution was then cooled and an equivalent quantity of an aqueous solution of potassium cyanate gradually added under shaking. The white precipitate thus obtained was crystallised from water; m.p. 223°. It is identical with compound (IX) as obtained by the action of urea. (Found: N, 33.56. $C_9H_{11}O_2N_5$ requires N, 33.49 per cent.)

1-Phenylcarbonylhydrazide-5-carbophenylamide, $PhNH \cdot NH \cdot CO \cdot NH \cdot NH \cdot CO \cdot NHPh$.—To a well cooled aqueous solution of 1-phenylcarbonylhydrazide (1 mol.), phenylisocyanate (1 mol.) was added drop by drop under shaking. A white precipitate was obtained almost instantaneously which was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 218–219°. (Found: N, 24.79. $C_{14}H_{15}O_2N_5$ requires N, 24.56 per cent.). When boiled with strong hydrochloric acid it was left quite unchanged.

1-Phenylcarbonylhydrazide-5-thiocarbophenylamide, $PhNH \cdot NH \cdot CO \cdot NH \cdot NH \cdot CS \cdot NHPh$.—An alcoholic solution of a mixture of molecular quantities of 1-phenylcarbonylhydrazide and phenyl mustard oil was heated under reflux for 15 minutes. A white precipitate was obtained which was filtered and washed with alcohol. It is almost insoluble in alcohol, acetic acid, and other organic solvents, except pyridine from which it is crystallised; m.p. 196° (decomp.) (yield quantitative). (Found: N, 23.10. $C_{14}H_{15}ON_5S$ requires N, 23.25 per cent.). The following compounds were prepared similarly and crystallised from large quantities of alcohol. They are all soluble in alkali and can be precipitated back by hydrochloric acid.

1-Phenylcarbonylhydrazide-5-thiocarbo-o-tolylamide, m.p. 175–176°. (Found: N, 22.28. $C_{15}H_{17}ON_5S$ requires N, 22.22 per cent.).

1-Phenylcarbonylhydrazide-5-thiocarbo-p-tolylamide, m.p. 196–197° (decomp.). (Found: N, 22.30. $C_{15}H_{17}ON_5S$ requires N, 22.22 per cent.).

1-Phenylcarbonylhydrazide-5-thiocarbo-1:3:4-xyllylamide, m.p. 179–180°. (Found: N, 21.40. $C_{16}H_{19}ON_5S$ requires N, 21.27 per cent.).

1-Phenylcarbonylhydrazide - 5 - thiocarboallylamide, m.p. 196°. (Found: N, 26.47. $C_{11}H_{15}ON_5S$ requires N, 26.41 per cent.).

1 - Phenylcarbonylhydrazide - 5 - thiocarbomethylamide, m.p. 207°. (Found: N, 27.74. $C_{10}H_{15}ON_5S$ requires N, 27.66 per cent.).

1-o-Tolylcarbonylhydrazide-5-thiocarbophenylamide, m.p. 194–195° (decomp.). (Found: N, 22.37. $C_{15}H_{17}ON_5S$ requires N, 22.29 per cent.).

1-o-Tolylcarbohydrazide-5-thiocarbo-o-tolylamide, m.p. 189°. (Found: N, 21.42. $C_{16}H_{19}ON_3S$ requires N, 21.27 per cent.)

1-o-Tolylcarbohydrazide-5-thiocarbo-p-tolylamide, m.p. 213°. (Found: N, 21.19. $C_{16}H_{19}ON_3S$ requires N, 21.27 per cent.)

1-o-Tolylcarbohydrazide-5-thiocarbo-1:3:4-xylylamide, m.p. 186°. (Found: N, 20.52. $C_{17}H_{21}ON_3S$ requires N, 20.40 per cent.)

1-o-Tolylcarbohydrazide-5-thiocarboallylamide, m.p. 197°. (Found: N, 25.19. $C_{12}H_{17}ON_3S$ requires N, 25.09 per cent.)

1-o-Tolylcarbohydrazide-5-thiocarbo- β -naphthylamide, m.p. 94–96°. (Found: N 19.25. $C_{19}H_{19}ON_3S$ requires N, 19.17 per cent.)

2-Keto-5-phenylimino-2:3:4:5-tetrahydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole (XI).

(a) Phenylcarbohydrazide-5-thiocarbophenylamide (5 g.) on being heated with strong hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) under reflux on a water-bath for an hour went into solution with the separation of a tarry mass which solidified on cooling. The solid was crystallised twice from acetone, m.p. 246°. It is insoluble in acids and alkalis. (Found: N, 21.82. $C_9H_7ON_3S$ requires N, 21.76 per cent.)

The hydrochloric acid solution after cooling yielded a precipitate which was proved to be phenylhydrazine hydrochloride by preparing the benzaldehyde derivative.

(b) Phenylcarbohydrazide-5-thiocarbophenylamide (5 g.) suspended in water was heated with an excess of ferric chloride solution for an hour on a water-bath, when a tar-like substance was obtained which solidified on cooling. It was filtered, washed with water and triturated in a mortar with dilute alkali. The insoluble substance was again filtered, washed with water and crystallised thrice from alcohol, m.p. 246° (yield 1 g.). It was insoluble in acids and alkalis and was found to be identical with the above compound.

2-Phenylhydrazino-5-anilino-2:3:4:5-tetrahydro-1:3:4-oxdiazole (XII).—Phenylcarbohydrazide-5-thiocarbophenylamide (5 g.) was heated with 20% potassium hydroxide (about 40 c.c.) on a water-bath for about an hour and a half. At first it went into solution, then a precipitate came out which was washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 244–245° (yield 1 g.). It is insoluble in acids and alkalis. (Found: N, 26.4. $C_{14}H_{13}ON_3$ requires N, 26.21 per cent.)

Action of strong Hydrochloric Acid or Ferric Chloride upon 1-Phenylcarbohydrazide-5-thiocarbo-o-tolylamide: Formation of 5-Tolyl-amino-2-keto-2:3-dihydro-1:3:4-thiodiazole.—The method of treatment and isolation of the reaction product was the same as in the

case of the corresponding phenyl compound. The substance was insoluble in acid and alkali and was twice crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 220—221°. (Found: N, 20·32. $C_9H_9ON_3S$ requires N, 20·29 per cent.)

Treatment with ferric chloride under the aforesaid conditions resulted in the formation of an identical compound.

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